

Cardioplegia in Cardiac Surgery and Cardiopulmonary Bypass

A Clinical Overview for Perfusion Practice

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April 27, 2026

Introduction

Cardioplegia refers to the intentional and temporary arresting of the heart to provide a bloodless and motionless surgical field for cardiac surgery. Cardioplegia protects the heart from ischemic injury thereby protecting the myocardium. Objectives of Cardioplegia are as follows-

1. Protection of the Myocardium
2. Prevention of Ischemic Injury.
3. Rapidly arrest the heart.
4. Provide a motionless field during Cardiac Surgery.
5. To reduce myocardial oxygen consumption.

Classification of Cardioplegia

A) Dependent on Delivery Method

- a) Antegrade
- b) Retrograde
- c) Direct Ostial

B) Dependent on Temperature

- a) Cold
- b) Warm
- c) Tepid

C) Dependent on Dosage

- a) Single
- b) Multiple
- c) Frequent

D) Dependent on Composition

- a) Blood
- b) Crystalloid

Dependent on Delivery Method

- a) Antegrade Cardioplegia
Antegrade Cardioplegia is administered via ostial root or the coronary arteries. The flow of antegrade cardioplegia is

along the coronary flow. It is the most common method of cardioplegia delivery.

b) Retrograde Cardioplegia

Retrograde Cardioplegia is administered via the coronary sinus. It is useful in surgeries like, Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting, Aortic Regurgitation and Coronary Blockage.

c) Direct Ostial Cardioplegia

Direct Ostial Cardioplegia is administered directly into the coronary ostia and is useful during aortic valve surgery.

c) Frequent Dose Cardioplegia

Frequent Dose Cardioplegia is administered at shorter intervals in small volumes, especially in high-risk patients.

Dependent on Temperature

a) Warm Cardioplegia

Temperature is ranges from 37°C to 38°C.

b) Cold Cardioplegia

Temperature ranges from 4°C to 10°C. Cold Cardioplegia is most commonly used as it provides better myocardial protection and reduces myocardial oxygen and metabolic demand.

Dependent on Dosage

a) Single Dose Cardioplegia

Single Dose Cardioplegia is administered only once and provides prolonged myocardial protection. It usually lasts for 60-120 minutes.

c) Tepid Cardioplegia

Temperature is ranges from 28°C to 32°C.

b) Multiple Dose Cardioplegia

Multiple Dose Cardioplegia is administered more than once, at regular intervals, to arrest the heart. It is administered typically, every 15 to 30 minutes.

Dependent on Composition

a) Crystalloid Cardioplegia

Crystalloid Cardioplegia contains electrolyte based solution.

For example- St. Thomas, Del Nido & HTK- Histidine-

tryptophan-ketoglutarate
(Custodiol)

b) Blood Cardioplegia

Blood Cardioplegia consists of Oxygenated Blood and Crystalloid Cardioplegia in the ration of 4:1 respectively. There are two types of blood cardioplegia-

- i. Warm Blood
Cardioplegia
- ii. Cold Blood
Cardioplegia

Types of Cardioplegia

1. St. Thomas Cardioplegia

St. Thomas Cardioplegia was developed in the St. Thomas Hospital, London in 1975. It is the most commonly used multi-dose Cardioplegia. There are two types of St. Thomas Cardioplegia-

- a. St. Thomas I Solution
Original Cardioplegia with high Potassium Concentration.
- b. St. Thomas II Solution
Modified Cardioplegia with low Calcium Concentration.

Preparation of St. Thomas CPG-

20 mL of St. Thomas CPG is mixed with 1L Ringer Lactate.

Composition of St. Thomas

CPG-

Potassium (K), Magnesium (Mg), Calcium (Ca) and Bicarbonate (HCO_3^-)

Arresting time of St. Thomas

CPG-

20-30 minutes

2. Del Nido Cardioplegia

Del Nido Cardioplegia was developed by Dr. Pedro J. Del Nido in the early 1990's. It is a single dose modified blood-crystalloid cardioplegia. It is used mostly during pediatric and adult cardiac surgeries.

Preparation of Del Nido CPG-

Crystalloid Base containing-
(Mixed with blood)-

- i. Mannitol ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$)
- ii. Magnesium (Mg)
- iii. Lidocaine ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}$)
- iv. Potassium (K)
- v. Sodium Bicarbonate
(NaHCO_3^-)

Arresting Time-

60-90 minutes

3. HTK (Custodiol) Cardioplegia

HTK (Custodiol) Cardioplegia was developed by Hans Jürgen

Bretschneider at the University of Göttingen in the early 1970's. It is a long-acting cardioplegia used during long and time taking cardiac surgeries. HTK stands for- Histidine-typtophan-ketogluterate.

Preparation of HTK CPG-

Ready made solution

Composition of HTK CPG-

- i. Histidine
- ii. Tryptophan
- iii. Ketogluterate
- iv. Mannitol

Arresting time of HTK CPG-

2 to 3 hours.

Complications of Cardioplegia

Although cardioplegia arrests the heart, lowers myocardial metabolic and oxygen demand

and protects fr om ischemic injury, it also may have some detrimental effects, if prepared incorrectly or due to incorrect delivery method. Few are mentioned below.

a) Inadequate Myocardial Protection

Inadequate myocardial protection occurs when cardioplegia is delivered incorrectly.

b) Cardiac Arrhythmia

Cardiac Arrhythmia take place due to electrolytic imbalance.

c) Myocardial Edema

Excessive administration of cardioplegia can lead to myocardial edema.

d) Myocardial Stunning

Prolonged Ischemia